

On the (in)visibility of librarians in third space literature

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DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17844973>

This piece was part of the Slowposium as a blog post, hence its more conversational tone. In it, I discuss my personal experience as an academic librarian encountering the idea of “third space(s)”.

When I was introduced to the concept of “third space” work in universities, I had an immediate reaction of “That’s me!” As an academic librarian I am a member of the university’s professional staff, but I teach workshops, set assessment, create learning objects, and collaborate with academics on elements of the curriculum. As a Law Librarian I have a set of Legal Research Competencies that I work to make sure students have learned by the end of their time in our law degrees. This seems to me to fall squarely within the definition of third space – summarised by Thorpe and Partridge (2024) as where “professional and academic staff cross into the others’ domain, or are engaged in activities that encompass both academic and professional activities”.

However, very little of the existing literature discusses librarians or librarianship in relation to third space. Thorpe and Partridge’s recent scoping review (2024), which looked at peer-reviewed articles from 2000 to 2022, brought up very few articles about library staff, and beyond one reference to “librarians in academic tenured roles” (Thorpe & Partridge, 2024, What is third space work? section) there was no identification within the discussion portion of the review of librarians or library staff as relevant to the discussion at all.

Another scoping review (Veles et al., 2023), referred to in Thorpe and Partridge’s work, covers a slightly shorter period of time between 2000 and 2020. This review looked only at professional staff, and identified far more articles about librarians, but the review was focused on professional identity and included “third space” as a possible descriptor of professional staff, rather than focusing on “third space” itself. Consequently, librarians were captured in this review as “professional staff” where they hadn’t been captured in a search focused on the third space. Fair or not, this seems to confirm my sense of librarians being forgotten in discussions of the third space despite clearly fitting the definition.

I have a few theories on why this is.

Perhaps part of the invisibility comes from the assumption that the third space is only for ways of operating that are new and disruptive and something that hasn’t been done before? After all, liaison librarians have been quietly doing their jobs for a long time now – Duane Wilson’s historical overview of the position dates the current form to the 1940s (2024, p. 1) – perhaps too quietly (as discussed by McCartin and Wright-Mair, 2022).

It’s also quite possible that there are some vocabulary conflicts involved. Libraries are part of a broader sector in which “third space” has an entirely different meaning as a physical space that is

not home (first space) or school or workplace (second space) (Wood, 2020). Libraries as physical spaces available to the public have a particular (although not always recognised) status as third places where it is not necessary to spend money, unlike shopping centres or movie theatres. Because of this vocabulary conflict it's actually quite difficult to search for "third space" and "library or librarian" as the majority of results will be about the broader meaning, rather than the university-specific one.

Finally, there may be geographical differences as to whether librarians are part of the third space at all. The discussion by McCartin and Wright-Mair covers some of the debate over librarians' status as "faculty" (academic) or professional in the USA (2022), but in Australia most academic librarians are classified as professional staff. (I work at an institution where academic status was removed from librarians in 2015.) Where librarians are academic staff, the question of being third space workers wouldn't arise – but in Australia, we decidedly are part of third space.

Why does any of this matter?

As an academic librarian who sees myself and the challenges of my role reflected in the definition of third space, the general lack of third space literature that mentions librarians seems like a gap. I'd like to see more discussions of the challenges of teaching into subjects run by others; of having teaching and even assessment responsibilities that are barely even acknowledged; and of how this has been a fact of academic librarianship for a long, long time.

References

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